

Grant Agreement Number: 768953

Project acronym: ICT4CART

Project full title: ICT Infrastructure for Connected and Automated

Road Transport

D 9.6

Communication Tools (Version II)

Due delivery date: 31 August 2020

Actual delivery date: 01 September 2020

Organization name of lead participant for this deliverable: ERTICO

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the GSA)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the GSA)	
CO	Confidential , only for members of the consortium (including the GSA)	

Document Control Sheet

Deliverable number:	D9.6
Deliverable responsible:	ERT
Work package:	9
Editor:	Sophie Henkel - ERTICO

Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail
Sophia Adam	ICCS	sophia.adam@iccs.gr
Sophie Henkel	ERTICO	s.henkel@mail.ertico.com
Elena Krikigianni	SEAB	e.krikigianni@seability.eu

Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v.01	24/07/2019	Final version sent for approval to official reviewers	Sophie Henkel (ERTICO)
v.02	21/08/2020	Version with comments sent by the reviewers	Elena Krikigianni (SEAB) Sophia Adam (ICCS)
v.03	31/08/2020	Final version with comments addressed sent to the coordinator for final revision and submission	Sophie Henkel (ERTICO)

Abstract
<p>This document presents an update of all the Communication tools currently available and foreseen in the future to promote ICT4CART to target audiences. The communication tools, included in this deliverable, are part of the project’s communication and dissemination strategy and, together with its brand identity, have the aim of ensuring the maximum diffusion and impact of relevant ICT4CART information, results and findings. The final version of the future tools will be reported in D9.3 “Definition of Communication Strategy and Plan (Version III)”, due in month 30.</p>

Legal Disclaimer

The document reflects only the authors’ view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MS	Microsoft
PO	Project officer
PPT	Power Point Presentation
R&I	Research and Innovation
Y	Year
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1	Purpose of the document	5
2	Communication Tools.....	5
2.1	Printed material.....	5
2.1.1	ICT4CART Printed material: to date	6
2.1.2	ICT4CART Printed material: foreseen products.....	10
2.2	Digital presence.....	10
2.2.1	Digital presence: to date	10
2.2.1.1	ICT4CART website	10
2.2.1.2	ICT4CART social media accounts.....	19
2.2.2	Digital presence: developed products.....	20
2.2.3	Digital presence: foreseen products	21
3	Conclusions.....	22

List of Figures

Figure 1:	ICT4CART roll-up banner.....	7
Figure 2:	ICT4CART Factsheet	8
Figure 3:	ICT4CART flagship flyer	9
Figure 4:	ICT4CART website: homepage/1	12
Figure 5:	ICT4CART website: homepage/2	13
Figure 6:	ICT4CART website: about.....	13
Figure 7:	ICT4CART website: Partners' detailed page.....	14
Figure 8:	ICT4CART website: objectives.....	15
Figure 9:	ICT4CART website: pilot sites landing page	16
Figure 10:	ICT4CART website: deliverables.....	17
Figure 11:	ICT4CART website: contacts & newsletter form.....	18
Figure 12:	ICT4CART LinkedIn group.....	19
Figure 13:	ERTICO Twitter account	19
Figure 14:	ICT4CART Twitter account	20
Figure 15:	ICT4CART Interview Series #1	21
Figure 16:	ICT4CART Corporate Video	21

1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an update on the ICT4CART Communication tools which have been developed since the beginning of the project and the ones foreseen throughout its implementation. Such tools have been created in the framework of the ICT4CART Communication Strategy and Plan, in order to provide the partners with effective instruments to promote and display project's results, findings and news, to build a solid off-line and on-line reputation and to represent ICT4CART during events, conferences and workshops' attendance. The Communication tools have also the objective of supporting the diffusion of ICT4CART's key messages, which have been detailed in D9.1 "Definition of Communication Strategy and Plan" (Version I), to each audience's target group. In addition, this deliverable represents a useful summary of all available instruments to pursue the objective of ICT4CART promotion and dissemination for the project's consortium.

The tools presented in this document have been updated and developed as needed throughout the project lifecycle and implementation, since reported in D9.5 "Communication tools (Version I)", due in M06. Their development and impact will be further presented in D9.3 "Definition of Communication Strategy and Plan" (Version III), due in M30.

Communication tools can be used freely by all consortium members, however all external bodies, except for the European Commission, must acquire the required permission from the consortium, before proceeding with any use of the ICT4CART material.

2 Communication Tools

2.1 Printed material

Printed material is an effective way to promote and showcase the project's core objectives and main facts during conferences, workshops and events the consortium organises or participates in. Printed material is useful to build a significant offline presence, raising awareness and interest among the audience and giving them an opportunity to learn more about the project and take contact with the consortium.

ICT4CART printed material has been produced throughout the project implementation, tailoring the new products and adapting the existing ones according to its evolution and needs, to guarantee a significant and effective dissemination at relevant events.

All materials conform to the project visual identity, ensuring the correct use of the logo, colour palette, fonts and brand identity, as detailed in D9.1.

Moreover, all printed products will comply with EC visual regulation for H2020 R&I co-funded

actions, displaying the official EU logo and disclaimer, as demanded and with an appropriate prominence¹.

2.1.1 ICT4CART Printed material: to date

As of M24 (August 2020), the following Communication tools have been developed and are available for dissemination purposes:

- One ICT4CART roll-up banner (see Figure 1 below): the roll-up banner highlights the project's tagline, which can be considered as summarising the common ICT4CART main goal: "A Connected Future for Automated Driving". The concept picture and overall design have been carefully selected to depict ICT4CART in a consistent way, as suggested in the project's brand identity and guidelines; the short text included in the banner puts an accent to one of ICT4CART's pillar: the cooperation between different industry sectors to achieve the common goal of a higher level of driving automation. The roll-up includes all 21 partners' logos, and will be used by each of them in several occasion in which ICT4CART will have a fixed presence, i.e. exhibitions, demonstrations, conferences etc. The roll-up has been updated and will be re-printed as consortium member logos changed since the beginning of the project. The promotion of the valuable asset represented by each of ICT4CART partner enhances the impact of this product and its capacity of raising interest among the audience about the project's future achievements, motivating the public to follow ICT4CART implementation and get in contact with the consortium;
- One ICT4CART factsheet (see Figure 2 below): the project factsheet is an efficient dissemination and communication product that provides the targeted audiences with all the relevant information in a clear and concise way, and yet not missing any of it. The visuals are in line with the project's brand identity and colours, and the one-page format makes it an ideal instrument to be distributed during relevant events and other dissemination occasions;
- One ICT4CART flagship flyer (see Figure 3 below): the flyer has been developed using the project's factsheet's concept, to ensure a visual and content consistency among all ICT4CART communication tools and products, but with the idea of offering a more complete and extended version of it. In addition to the project's objectives, partners' logos, contact details, this recto/verso trifold includes more details about ICT4CART challenges, solutions and architecture. A map depicting the four test sites and a section dedicated to the impact are also included. The flagship flyer will be used as additional dissemination material to be

¹ Participant Portal Online Manual, Acknowledgement of EU funding:
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grantmanagement/%20acknowledge-funding_en.htm

distributed during relevant events and other occasions.

ICT4CART

A connected future for Automated Driving

Design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure to enable higher levels of automation

OUR PARTNERS

 [ICT4CART](#)
 [@ict4cart_eu](#)

www.ict4cart.eu

 ICT4CART project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement No. 768953. Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

design: www.beismpul.com

Figure 1: ICT4CART roll-up banner

ICT4CART

A Connected Future for Automated Driving

AT A GLANCE

Design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure to enable higher levels of automation

ICT elements

- HYBRID CONNECTIVITY
- DATA MANAGEMENT
- CYBERSECURITY
- DATA PRIVACY
- ACCURATE LOCALISATION

Test sites

Test sites in Austria, Germany and Italy
Cross border interoperability at the Italian-Austrian border

Facts and figures

- 21 Partners
- 9 EU Countries
- 36 months duration
- 10.2M EUR total budget

www.ict4cart.eu

 @ict4cart_eu

 ICT4CART

- High-value use cases, demonstrated and validated under real-life conditions
- Hybrid communication approach where all the major wireless technologies are integrated under a flexible "sliced" network architecture
- Seamless integration between all actors from 3 different industries

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION:

Dr. Angelos Amditis
ICT4CART Coordinator
Research Director, ICCS
a.amditis@iccs.gr

Sophie Henkel
ICT4CART Communications and Dissemination Manager
s.henkel@mail.ertico.com

 ICT4CART project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement No. 768953. Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Figure 2: ICT4CART Factsheet

OUR PARTNERS

PROJECT COORDINATOR
Dr. Angelos Amditis
 ICT4CART Coordinator
 Research Director, ICCS
 a.amdits@iccs.gr

DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION MANAGER
Cordelia Wilson
 ICT4CART Communications and
 Dissemination Manager
 c.wilson@mail.ertico.com

ICT4CART
 @ict4cart_eu
 www.ict4cart.eu

**A connected future
for Automated Driving**

THE PROJECT

ICT4CART intends to address the ICT-related challenges of road automation and telecommunications that are linked with connectivity, data management, interoperability, cyber-security, privacy and ICT architecture.

ICT4CART aims at creating an ICT infrastructure to enable the transition towards road transport automation, adapting and improving technological advances from different industries, mainly telecom, automotive and IT.

ICT4CART SOLUTIONS

ICT4CART builds on four specific high-value use cases, which will be demonstrated and validated under real-life conditions at project test sites.

ICT4CART adopts a hybrid communication approach where all the major wireless technologies, i.e. cellular, ITS-G5 and LTE-V, are integrated under a flexible "sliced" network architecture. This architecture will ensure performance and resilience for different groups of applications according to the needs of higher levels of automation.

A distributed IT environment for data aggregation and analytics will be implemented. This offers seamless integration and exchange of data and services between all the different actors.

TEST SITES

Austria
 Germany
 Italy
 Italian-Austrian border

CHALLENGES

- Limited availability of short range communications
- Network overload in high crowded environments
- Lack of hybrid connectivity development
- Lack of EU cross-border testing activities
- Lack of standards for vehicles Environmental Perception Model
- Non interoperable and standard data exchanging system
- Lack of a pan-European cyber-security mechanism for connected and automated driving
- Insufficient data privacy mechanisms
- Scarce availability of finance and land use limitations for upgrading civil infrastructure

THE ARCHITECTURE

COMMUNICATION
 - LTE/5G
 - ITS-G5
 - Fibre

SLICES
 - High throughput
 - Standard
 - Low latency
 - No slicing

RSU
 - Sensor

IMPACT

- A performant and resilient architecture for different groups of applications
- Seamless integration and exchange of data and services
- Cyber-security and data privacy
- Accurate localisation services
- Standardisation and interoperability
- Enabling the transition to higher levels of automation
- New business opportunities

Figure 3: ICT4CART flagship flyer

2.1.2 ICT4CART Printed material: foreseen products

During the project lifecycle, further printed material may be produced as needed and agreed among the consortium members, to attend/host specific events relevant for ICT4CART successful communication and dissemination activities.

As foreseen in the GA, a set of ICT4CART roll-up banners will be developed throughout the project's implementation. Since the participation to events has come to a complete halt due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the development of said roll-up banners will continue at a later stage in the project.

The additional products will be included in D9.3 ("Definition of Communication Strategy and Plan Version III), due respectively in M30.

2.2 Digital presence

ICT4CART's digital presence is ensured by a dedicated website and other relevant social media platforms to enhance the impact of its communication and dissemination activities. Such online presence ensures an effective and efficient communication of ICT4CART news, results and events, in order to maximise the project's impact and outreach and to involve the widest audience possible throughout its implementation.

2.2.1 Digital presence: to date

2.2.1.1 ICT4CART website

ICT4CART's website domain is www.ict4cart.eu.

The project's website has been designed with the purpose of creating a visually appealing, user-friendly information hub, complying with EC's requirements and able to convey ICT4CART's messages to the interested audience.

The website's design has been carefully selected to follow ICT4CART's brand identity: all visual elements have been created by deconstructing the project's logo and placing its components in the website's space, to create a well recognisable visual pattern and, next to it, a road/path to follow while browsing among ICT4CART's information.

The website includes several sections, providing information about the consortium, the project's objectives, the pilot sites, the social media links and the contact details.

In addition, a dedicated "Hub" section features the latest publications related to the project. The project's newsletter, press releases, project presentation, reports, papers are available for the website user to view. They are updated continuously. Furthermore, visual material such as a photo gallery of events and printed material can be accessed via the "Hub" section. Lastly, the "Hub" also offers all the articles from international press related to ICT4CART activities and implementation,

deliverables of all WP's for download as well as a media kit.

ICT4CART's website follows the structure below (please refer also to Figure 4 to 11 below):

- About;
- Objectives;
- Pilots;
- News;
- Hub;
- Contacts.

These main sections include several sub-pages to gather future and past events, partners' descriptions, links to social media with a preview of the latest news and posts, a subscription box to the project's newsletter, which is issued annually.

The above-mentioned sections will be updated and enriched throughout the project's lifecycle, to ensure an effective flow of information for consortium partners and users.

With regards to figures, the website to date is exceeding the set KPI's of 100 unique visitors per month, with currently approximately 250 unique visitors per month (Status in August 2020). The top three pages clicked following the homepage being the 1) pilots page, 2) about page, 3), objectives page.

Figure 4: ICT4CART website: homepage/1

Figure 5: ICT4CART website: homepage/2

Figure 6: ICT4CART website: about

The screenshot shows the ICT4CART website's 'Partners' detailed page for SEAbility. The page layout includes a top navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Objectives', 'Pilots', 'News', 'Hub', and 'Contact'. A left sidebar lists various partners, with 'Seability' highlighted in green. The main content area features the SEAbility logo, a section titled 'Role in the project' describing their involvement in task 9.2, and a section titled 'About SEAbility-SEAB' detailing their history and services. At the bottom, there is a 'Follow us online' section with links to the official website and social media profiles on Twitter and LinkedIn.

Figure 7: ICT4CART website: Partners' detailed page

ICT4CART

About Objectives Pilots News Hub Contact

Objectives

The goal of ICT4CART will be achieved through the following objectives. The relevant project Work Packages (WPs) are listed at the end of each objective description.

- 01** Identify the functional and technical connectivity requirements posed by the needs of higher levels of automation (SAE L3 & L4) ensuring communication redundancy and increased reliability.
- 02** Implement and test a standards-based distributed IT environment for data aggregation capable of collecting and managing in an automated and interoperable way all the exchanged data regarding the driver, the vehicle, the vulnerable road users (VRUs) and the infrastructure, leveraging also cloud technology.
- 03** Implement cyber-security and data protection and privacy mechanisms aligned with the EU policy objectives.
- 04** Improve localisation by combining information from different sources (European GNSS, on board sensors, other vehicles, infrastructure, etc.) and adapt existing tools and algorithms for data fusion.
- 05** Validate and demonstrate the ICT Infrastructure architecture through the project use cases and test sites.

Figure 8: ICT4CART website: objectives

Figure 9: ICT4CART website: pilot sites landing page

The screenshot shows the ICT4CART website's 'Deliverables' page. At the top left is the ICT4CART logo. The navigation menu includes 'About', 'Objectives', 'Pilots', 'News', 'Hub' (which is underlined), and 'Contact'. Below the navigation is a breadcrumb trail: 'Home - Hub - Deliverables'. The main heading reads 'Deliverables will be updated throughout the project implementation'. A secondary navigation bar contains 'Press releases', 'In the media', and 'Deliverables' (which is underlined). The deliverables are listed in three sections, each with a green circular icon containing a white label (WP1, WP2, WP3) and a blue plus or minus icon on the right. The first section is 'Project management'. The second section is 'Requirements and initial market analysis'. The third section is 'Ict Architecture for connected & automated traffic', which is expanded to show four sub-deliverables: D3.1: ICT4CART Reference Architecture, D3.2: Flexible Networks Specifications and Architecture, D3.3: IT Environment Specifications and Architecture, and D3.4: Cyber-security and data privacy Specifications and Architecture. Each sub-deliverable includes a brief description and a 'Download' link.

ICT4CART

About Objectives Pilots News Hub Contact

Home - Hub - Deliverables

Deliverables will be updated throughout the project implementation

Press releases In the media Deliverables

WP1 Project management +

WP2 Requirements and initial market analysis +

WP3 Ict Architecture for connected & automated traffic -

D3.1 : ICT4CART Reference Architecture
A report specifying the reference architecture of ICT4CART, including communication, data (IT), and cyber-security & privacy.
[Download](#)

D3.2 : Flexible Networks Specifications and Architecture
A report including the architecture and specifications of the communication infrastructure considering the various networks.
[Download](#)

D3.3 : IT Environment Specifications and Architecture
A report specifying the IT environment architecture, including data exchange flows and interfaces, management, and analytics, semantic interoperability, and high precision positioning.
Coming soon

D3.4 : Cyber-security and data privacy Specifications and Architecture
A report specifying the architecture and the specifications for cyber-security and data privacy bricks, including solutions for privacy-friendly-authentication, role-based IAM and cyber-security situation awareness.
Coming soon

Figure 10: ICT4CART website: deliverables

Home About Objectives Pilots Hub Contact

Home > Contact

Contact us

Do you want to learn more about ICT4CART? Don't hesitate to reach us through the contacts below or subscribe to our newsletter (available from end of Y1).

Project contact details

ICCS	ERTICO-ITS Europe
ICT4CART Coordinator, Research Director, ICCS	ICT4CART Communications and Dissemination Manager
Angelos Amditis	Sophie Herikati
+30 210 772 1665	+32 2 400 07 00

Subscribe to our newsletter

Receive announcements, business and networking opportunities, invitations to events and workshops as well as advocacy papers.

First name
 Last name

Email
 Phone number (optional)

Country (optional)

Figure 11: ICT4CART website: contacts & newsletter form

2.2.1.2 ICT4CART social media accounts

Since the beginning of the project, the following social channels have been launched and utilised to promote ICT4CART content:

- ICT4CART LinkedIn group (“ICT4CART”, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13642288/>), a community and facilitator for partners and stakeholders’ discussions and idea exchanges. ERTICO is responsible of its maintenance and update with relevant information. The LinkedIn group counts, as of August 2020, 68 members (see Figure 12 below).
- Two different Twitter accounts:
 1. **ERTICO** (@ERTICO, <https://twitter.com/ERTICO>), with 7,494 followers as of August 2020 (see Figure 13 below);
 2. **ICT4CART** dedicated Twitter account (@ict4cart, <https://twitter.com/ict4cart>), managed by SEABILITY in coordination with ICCS, counting 213 followers as of August 2020 (see Figure 14 below).

Figure 12: ICT4CART LinkedIn group

Figure 13: ERTICO Twitter account

Figure 14: ICT4CART Twitter account

All social media accounts comply with the guidelines provided in the EC Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects².

2.2.2 Digital presence: developed products

As of M24 (August 2020), the following products for digital presence have been developed:

- a regular e-newsletter is published annually, in October, starting from the end of the first year of the project, including the most relevant information, outcomes and results together with attended and upcoming events. It was agreed by the consortium members to issue the newsletter annually, instead of one every six months. This decision was made in order to ensure that the readers and subscribers are provided with relevant and useful content. The first newsletter can be viewed [here](#). ERTICO coordinates this activity;
- “Meet ICT4CART” Interview Series – monthly interviews with consortia members, published on the [ICT4CART website](#) and disseminated on the ICT4CART LinkedIn Group, ICT4CART Twitter account, ERTICO Twitter account, ICT4CART Newsletter and ERTICO Newsletter;
- one professional video – an ICT4CART corporate video has been produced and is available on the [ICT4CART website](#), the ERTICO YouTube channel and the SEABility YouTube channel. It has also been disseminated across the ICT4CART Social Media channels and will be included

² H2020 Programme: Guidance, Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-medguide_en.pdf

in the annual newsletter.

Figure 15: ICT4CART Interview Series #1

Figure 16: ICT4CART Corporate Video

2.2.3 Digital presence: foreseen products

With the aim of enhancing the impact and effectiveness of ICT4CART communication and dissemination activities, the GA foresees additional digital material to be developed at a later stage,

namely:

- short videos to be created. A video campaign will follow after the ICT4CART Interview Series with each consortium partner providing short statements;
- ICT4CART giveaways with QR code linking to the project website. Due to the complete halt of face to face meetings and events in view of the COVID-19 pandemic, the development of giveaways has been postponed to a later stage of the project. They will be available at demo sites and at the final event of the project.

3 Conclusions

This deliverable presented ICT4CART Communication Tools (Version II), which will be used as set of instruments for the consortium members to disseminate ICT4CART and maximize its impact.

This deliverable described the material that has been already produced since the project's start, and the additional products foreseen to be developed throughout ICT4CART's implementation, as described in the GA but also as it may be needed/useful for the project's future developments.

Due to the extraordinary circumstances faced by the current COVID-19 pandemic, some of the planned project activities such as attendance of events have come to a halt, which resulted in postponing the development some of the Communication tools, in particular printed materials.

The development of the tools described in this deliverable will be reported in D9.3 Definition of Communication Strategy and Plan (Version III), due in month 30.